

Human Dualism in the Morality of Truth

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Abstract

Man is always bound to the source of truth, both when making decisions and as a guide to life. The source of truth today is still a unique debate by people from different backgrounds and points of view. This paper discusses human dualism in moral truth seen in terms of philosophy, individuals in society, and human dilemma exposure in deciding right and wrong. This paper also reveals the truth of morality in accordance with the study of human philosophy.

Keywords: philosophy, morality of truth, moral relativism, moral objectivism, social science

Introduction: The Fundamental Paradigm of Man

Humans fundamentally possess a paradoxical dualism that is projected in various works, ideas, and behavioral patterns. This dualism includes autonomy-dependence, relative-absolute, and free-bound (Tumanggor, Kholis, & Nurochim, 2014). Humans also have an essence. The essence of humans means the basic or essential element that gives value to humans, which becomes an integral part that is inseparable from the human self (Sabdon, 2019). The essence of humans is active-creative, where humans have the potential to recognize who they are and why they exist in the world. So far, understanding about the essence of humans is classified into several streams, among others: materialism, idealism, and realism. **Materialism** is the thought that matter is the only reality. Thus, everything can occur through a material process. This stream was first developed by Ludwig Feuerbach (1804-1872) as a form of rejection

of Hegel's philosophy (1770-1830) (Hadiwijono, 2016). Feuerbach stated that the most important thing in humans is a natural creature (physical). All efforts are driven by lust within him, which is the urge to live. Therefore, human reason and knowledge are merely tools to achieve success and happiness. Human effort is what makes humans live. Human life can only occur in the material nature (Hardiman, 2007). Therefore, metaphysics and religion or anything related to spirituality must be rejected. The same thing was also stated by Marx (1818-1893). Although Marx agreed with Feuerbach's opinion about the element of humans as *Gattung* (natural creatures), Marx's opinion about religion was different. Religion according to Marx is a projection of the human condition influenced by poor economic conditions and as a tool for human consolation. Religion has given an illusion of a better life in Heaven (Linnemann, 1991). Marx did not reject religion, but Marx considered that the religious system would disappear if the economic needs of society were met.

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For materialists, humans recognize who they are and their existence based on their material circumstances. Next is **Idealism**, as proposed by Kant (1724-1801), Fichte (1762-1814), Schelling (1775-1854), Hegel (1770-1831), and Schopenhauer (1788-1860). The philosophy of idealism is very different from what is proposed by materialism. According to the idealism stream, what becomes reality is the “idea” and not the material. This idea is spiritual/intelligent. In addition, according to idealism, humans are spiritual beings (souled) (Tumanggor, Kholis, & Nurochim, 2014), so spiritual matters are more important than material matters (Brown, 2017; Brown, 2018). Idealism originated from Kant’s view of *das Ding an sich* (the thing in itself) which is considered to have a problem of inconsistency (Hardiman, 2007). The first problem is that *das Ding an sich* cannot be a ‘cause’ or causality because its nature transcends knowledge. Then the second problem is that the determination of *das Ding an sich* will be dangerous if Kant sets it as something deterministic. This means, Kant will actually be trapped in a dogmatic attitude that he actually wants to criticize. The next factor is the influence of theology and romanticism (Hardiman, 2007). In idealism, values such as the relationship between God and humans, Heaven and Hell, and life and death undergo a kind of ‘demythologization’ or ‘rationalization’ so that they become philosophical speculation. Just as the relationship between God and humans becomes a relationship between the absolute and the relative. Romanticism also influences idealism by its way of viewing nature as a living organism totality, *Volkgeist* (people’s soul), and various cultural manifestations caused by *Volkgeist* (Hardiman, 2007). For idealists, humans recognize who they are and their existence based on the existence of their soul’s spirituality. The last is the stream of **Realism** Philosophy. Realism eclectically views humans as both material and spiritual beings. Both are original and eternal essences (Tumanggor, Kholis, & Nurochim, 2014). Realism has two theses. The first thesis is the existence of entities or called the *existence thesis*. The second thesis is its objective

existence and independence. This thesis can also be referred to as the *independent thesis* (Brock & Mares, 2007). When idealism became the dominant philosophy at that time, subjectivism received protection and renewal, so realism emerged to counter this subjectivism (Holt, Marvin, & Montague, 1912). Realism philosophy opens opportunities to understand morality with the term moral realism. Moral realism briefly means a metaphysical thesis about the nature and status of morality and moral claims where existing moral facts and truths are considered objective with some meta-ethical provisions (Brink, 1989). For realists, humans recognize who they are and their existence based on understanding their nature (ego) and their moral state. Moral realism contains moral objectivism and relativism which will later become the center of debate about human truth dualism. (Kirchin, 2012)

The Position of Human Moral in Social Perspective

Human philosophy based on these three streams opens a question, “where is the moral position of humans?”. Before answering the above question, we must first understand morality and ethics, and their relationship with human philosophy. **Morality**, according to Bertens (2017:11), is a real dimension that only exists within humans, both at the individual and social stages. Humans have an awareness of good and bad. Awareness of good and bad is something common, a human phenomenon, and universal (Bertens, 2017). Meanwhile, the science that studies morality is called ethics. **Ethics** is briefly defined as a science that analyzes the scientific approach to moral behavior (Bertens, 2017; Tännsjö, 2002). It should also be noted that the term morality (lat. *mos*: singular or *mores*: plural) is interpreted only as a person’s outward behavior (Verkuyl, 2001), especially in social science studies (sociology). The use of the term *mores* in social science, along with usage, folkways, custom, and law, *mores* are categorized as a system of societal norms (code of conduct) to provide guidance for the

behavior of humans living in that society (Soekanto, 2013). These guidelines are constructed by society based on the assessment of customs or common practices (folkways) of good and bad or right and wrong. The origin of mores is unclear, it happens unplanned, but its existence is never denied because it receives traditional support and has informal and communal sanctions (Narwoko & Suyanto, 2014). The mores system also accommodates harsh prohibitions as taboo terms, if violated will receive moral condemnation and condemnation from society. Examples of taboos include: incestuous relationships, cheating, obscene words, forbidden food, or anything that violates the good interests of society. It can be concluded that mores are beliefs about right and wrong in behavior/actions (Horton & Hunt, 2006). This belief is considered by society as part of the essence of truth that must be obeyed. Meanwhile, not all societies have the same belief about “good”. Morals in society (hereinafter referred to as code of conduct) are found to be different, thus causing quite significant irrational perceptions. For example: men and women who are not married can live in the same house without being gossiped about by Western society. Conversely, insults and gossip occur in Eastern society. Because, the habit of living together without a marriage bond will disturb the good interests of that society. Often the difference in mores is categorized as a difference in culture or tradition, where culture as a creation of society has different characteristics, inherited from generation to generation. (Koentjaraningrat, 2015). The position of morals in social science lies in the manifest function, which is a behavior that can be traced by human senses. Morals in society are not abstract, can be realized in daily life, relative, and pluralistic. Society, borrowing Durkheim’s understanding, has a social force (social coercion) from collective consciousness that is exteriority (external) and constraint (coercion)

so that mores seem to come to humans with the obligation to obey it (Veeger, 1990).

Men and Dilemma of “Right and Wrong”

It’s important to remember that the reality of society is a collection of individual humans who cannot be separated (Veeger, 1990). Therefore, it is human existence that influences society, which in turn also influences individuals. Now let’s discuss human morality. Human morality is tested for its certainty through two approaches: objectivist and relativistic approaches² (Kurtinez & Gerwitz, 1992). The objectivist approach emerged in the classical age, where the world was seen as a result of natural forces (naturalistic), while reasoning was the foundation of knowledge that is absolute, objective, or certain. Classical age figures like Socrates and Plato emphasized that there are fixed and unchangeable moral values and norms (Bertens, 2017). Throughout the Middle Ages, thinking about objective morality tended to be more spiritualistic and less naturalistic, and was seen to be more based on faith than reasoning (Kurtinez & Gerwitz, 1992). Objective morality gets overshadowed by a relativistic orientation that will later become modern science. Because modern science has taken most of the main foundations of thought in the Western world, its epistemology is probabilistic and naturalistic (Kurtinez & Gerwitz, 1992)). This influences knowledge about morality and its truth is probabilistic, relativistic, and contingent (all by chance). The truth for modern morals does not care about the existence of a special device that is universal and objective. A common phenomenon we can feel is when faced with the decision of abortion. The assumption of this phenomenon is tended to be a reprehensible act because it is outside of marriage. However, the tendency that becomes a reprehensible act is biased by certain societies that have different concepts about

² Please note that there is a difference in intent between moral pluralism and moral relativism. Moral pluralism relates to the state of society (social science perspective). While

moral relativism is related to views or opinions. Other information that needs to be known is that the metaethical scope is included in moral realism.

abortion. The cause of abortion is the main basis for whether the practice is legal or illegal. According to a survey conducted by the Pew Research Center Religion & Public Life, as many as 61% of U.S. society in 2019 stated that abortion should be legalized (pro choice) for all or some cases and 39% stated abortion is illegal (pro life) for all or some cases³.

The same problems also occur related to other issues, such as: animal killing, slavery, adultery in marriage, and so on. In view of this, humans are always faced with the condition “where there is evil, there is good. Where there is good, there is evil”⁴. This situation continuously shapes human life values. Another issue is couples who change their nationality because in their home country they are not allowed to marry the same sex⁵. Changing nationality is considered a solutive attitude from a moral problem. The country being targeted is able to accommodate same-sex marriage so it does not become a moral problem in the society of that country.

Moral Relativism and Objectivism, Which is Right?

A rather complex debate is put forward by two streams of morality. First, we will discuss the perspective of moral relativism. Quoting a statement from Harman (1996) which states about moral relativism:

“There is no single true morality. There are many different moral frameworks, none of which is more correct than the others.”

The state of humans having a moral essence causes variations and differences in what is considered good and right. Moral relativism unites the state of moral values with its cultural state so that what is produced varies (Harman & Thomson, 1996).

The strong cultural state binds a person to act according to their culture (social force). The basic difference for relativists is: people who are different with different perspectives will rationally respond in different ways to the same evidence. Just as the classic question about heliocentric or geocentric, motion is something relative. There is nothing absolute because each particular is different (Harman & Thomson, 1996). For relativists, there is no term for “absolute” truth because every act can be judged right or wrong according to its moral coordinates. The same thing was also put forward by the Sophists in the discourse of 5th century BC philosophy. They problematize moral arguments to conclude that good - bad and right - wrong are just a matter of personal decision (Purnama, 2018). Moral relativism is often also stated to identify a moral system determined by a person’s values about “what is good and right”. As an example of relativity evaluation, in psychology, an extrovert is a person who likes crowds. Crowds and interactive attitudes are a source of energy for them. But, for introverts, crowds are something to be avoided as much as possible (Rosida & Astuti, 2015). For extroverts, crowds can support their activities because they involve many people. The crowd is “good” because it helps their condition to be productive (good based on a certain goal, what they want to achieve and the values they accept). If the extrovert states “working in a crowd is good” to the introvert, then what happens is: working in a crowd is good and benefits him and other extroverts. It’s just that, the “good” is not felt by the introvert because it is considered to disrupt their productivity. Crowds and communication with many people are something to be avoided as much as possible.

Moral relativism criticizes those who believe in absolutism that there are no standard standards and no morals are better than other morals. Each person

³ Taken from <https://www.pewforum.org/fact-sheet/public-opinion-on-abortion/> (Access July, 11th, 2020)

⁴The term is interpreted from St. Augustine's philosophical statement in his book "Confession" and the Chinese philosophy of "Yin-Yang".

⁵ Taken from <https://www.bbc.com/indonesia/majalah-48460701> (Access July 14th, 2020)

cares about the standard of value they hold. This situation often causes conflicts of affective-cognitive attitudes that can be resolved with certain agreements or agreements (Harman & Thomson, 1996). This affective attitude according to Harman is an attitude influenced by motivational drives and care, including hopes, desires, longings, fears, and hatred. While cognitive attitudes include: perception, belief, expectation, and denial. So, the conclusion of understanding moral relativism according to Harman:

- (1) Each individual has *moral coordinates* and *moral frameworks* from the cultural background that forms the basis for good and bad decisions.
- (2) There is no term for moral absolutism, each individual/group has a principle of what is considered right and all of them are equally right.
- (3) Each individual/group has a concern (careness) related to the moral they are fighting for until it causes a conflict of affective-cognitive attitudes. The conflict can be resolved with a certain agreement.

Regarding the truth conditions (truth conditions) in this moral relativism, Harman proposes a formula for assessment called *Quasi-absolutists* (Harman & Thomson, 1996; Stroud, 1998). Quasi-absolutists (can also be called projectivism or quasi-realism) are Harman's terminology to correct the flawed moral concept with his formula regarding relativism (Stroud, 1998). The flaw in question is the difficulty in expressing basic moral disagreement (basic moral) as a form of its main argument. An assessment of a moral argument can be judged right or wrong even though objectively it is not necessarily right or wrong. With an emphasis on language as an element of self-expression (emotivism approach), this quasi-absolutist assessment seems to (pretend) state that there is a single morality truth that is projected in the person's moral framework out (onto the world) (Stroud, 1998). The conclusion is that moral

relativism makes a lot of sense among various other moral diversity principles. Moral truth should accommodate unity, agreement (bargaining), and harmony of people who have different standards of truth.

The next discussion is about criticism of moral relativism. Summarizing moral relativism, different cultures will influence different value systems. There are two basic questions whether the values and norms in culture are based on *physis* (nature) or on *nomos* (rules or laws)? In fact, cultural institutions, including morals, are only based on customs or their *nomos* (Bertens, 2017). For them, a common act in a culture is the same as that act being morally good. Therefore, what is considered good in one place can be considered evil in another place. Bertens (2017) explains that *if moral relativism is true, then there can be no criticism between different moral practices*. This is because we believe that the ethical quality of each culture and society is different. For example: apartheid (racist) politics that are preserved in western countries are instead opposed and criticized in African countries. The sign is, it cannot be concluded that all moral principles in every place are equally true. Furthermore, *if moral relativism is true, then we only need to pay attention to the moral rules*. The moral must be considered perfect and there is no need to make a moral improvement. However, sometimes the values and norms in a culture need to be revised, considering that the morality of certain societies will lose their relevance with life that continues to change and become civilized. Examples such as: the use of animals as executors of the death penalty, full rights for men (gender discrimination), rituals that take victims, a culture of partying and war that spends a lot of money so that the community remains in a circle of poverty. The examples above, when viewed from an ethical point of view, the cultural value is not perfect. Finally, *if moral relativism is true, then there can be no progress in the field of morals*. A concrete example of slavery, colonialism and the aristocratic system that is now undergoing transformation. The

historical perspective states that this shows progress towards a more dignified morality. Thus, moral relativism does not stand the test. Because, the pattern of relativistic thinking is built on the basis of moral relativity, so it will collapse itself. So, in the norm (rule or benchmark) of morality there is something absolute or something that cannot be bargained (Bertens, 2017).

The rules in moral objectivism also oppose the subjectivism of truth. Subjectivity of truth can be interpreted as the freedom of *as you like* humans in determining right or wrong. Factors underlying this subjectivism include: interests, freedom, imagination, taste and self-ability. Even though in moral rules there is a subjective element, where moral norms direct themselves to the subject, but moral norms actually regulate humans and not vice versa. Morals do not depend on human tastes. In short, it can be concluded as follows:

- (1) Norms that are the result of moral values should be objective so that moral problems can be resolved and there is a point of agreement. If it's subjective, then there is no agreement because everything is considered right according to the subject's measure.
- (2) Objectively, moral values and norms are directed towards every individual/group without exception. That's why everyone should comply with the prevailing norms.
- (3) The subjective interpretation of *right-wrong* should be understood as a form of acceptance within humans. Here lies the conscience and free will as a very central assessment tool.

From the explanation of these two things, it can be concluded that morality is relative because it is related to its cultural state, objective because morality is external, and subjective because it is related to the moral meaning directed at the actor. This conclusion raises an important question, do these three moral elements inherently exist within humans? In relation to the dualistic and active-creative nature of humans, it is natural that humans in society have certain moral standards to judge good-bad, both in the cultural environment and the state of self subjectivity. A concrete example is a person with a disability who successfully gets out of their cultural state and subjective state.⁶ The standard used to assess their environment and subjective state must be based on something that is objective, absolute, and universal.

The Moral Position of Man in Materialism, Idealism and Realism.

The understanding of moral truth based on the streams of human philosophy in the early chapter should be understood. The first discussion is about morality in materialism. Materialism states that humans are formed by their material and physical conditions, as well as their production activities. Thus, materialistic morality states that all intrinsic goodness is contained in a person's production or consumption activities. Failure to buy (consumption) and make (production) goods is not only bad for the economy but also a moral failure (Moore, 2010)⁷. Materialistic morality is believed by people who rely on physical comfort and self-satisfaction as the highest good or ultimate goal in life (*summum bonum*). A person's parameters can state good or bad depending on the comfort of oneself and the profit or loss of the results

⁶ Quoted from <http://pattiro.org/en/2016/09/kesuksesan-aktivis-difabel-tingkatkan-akses-difabel-dan-masyarakat-miskin-di-lombok-barat-terhadap-kepesertaan-bpjs-kesehatan/> (Access September, 2nd 2020). It revealed that the success of difable activists in West Lombok opened opportunities for difables and the poor to get access to *Social Health Insurance Administration* Body (BPJS).

⁷ In this article, Moore discusses and criticizes David Brooke for his article on the US economic revival titled "Relax, We'll Be Fine" <https://www.nytimes.com/2010/04/06/opinion/06brooks.html?auth=login-google1tap&login=google1tap>. Moore disagrees with Brooke's assertion that his concept of morality does not make sense.

obtained. The second discussion is about moral idealism. This stream discusses the progressivity and the forming elements of human morality based on the idea or spiritual state without considering the physical element. Fichte (1762-1814) stated that the ideal moral is outside of humans, so humans must submit to that morality. The outside world becomes a burden for moral action. The content of its moral law is “do according to your heart”, because the heart does not mislead (Hadiwijono, 2016). The parameter of moral idealism for Fichte is where a person appreciates himself as a free being and has an obligation to respect others. For Kant, morality is everything that is external, which is in accordance with duty plus respect for decency (Hadiwijono, 2016). That’s where the position of morality in idealism. The last is about *morality in the stream of realism*. It has been mentioned before about moral objectivism and relativism as a model approach to understanding the position of human morality. Both of these are part of realism. While moral subjectivism is part of anti-realism (Brink, 1989). In general, good-bad statements in the stream of realism are moral facts for individuals and for everyone. Focusing on behavior as a fact and moral proposition (moral claims), moral realism not only describes what happens (*das sein*) but what should or should not happen (*das sollen*) (Kim, 1995). Moral realism also opens opportunities for humans to see and position right-wrong holistically and as it is (Brink, 1989).

Thus, it can be concluded that these three streams of human philosophy influence their morality. Humans, as explained in the previous chapter, must have an objective truth foundation to judge whether they themselves or their environment are good. Morality in materialism cannot answer the spiritual needs of humans. Considerations of good-bad humans are not only based on their material elements, but also related to their spiritual elements. Morality in idealism also cannot express good-bad as it is. The point is, moral idealism always lays a foundation that is ambiguous, double-meaning and non-verifiability (cannot be proven by the senses) (Robinson, 2018).

Moral realism has a more complete combination such as: cognitivism, descriptivism, success theory, literalism, and objectivism (Kim, 1995). Moral explanations can be more broadly and deeply put forward by this stream, because moral explanations are accompanied by objective moral facts while avoiding speculative justification of emotions and desires (Kim, 1995).

Conclusion

The dualism of right-wrong humans related to their morality can find its bright spot. Starting from understanding human philosophy. Human philosophy makes it easy for us to understand how human philosophy influences their moral state. Furthermore, the difference in moral consideration between individuals and society becomes an important point of this discussion. The state of society is influenced by cultural aspects so it is often trapped in relativity. Human morality should be able to correct what is considered right culturally and correct what is right subjectively. For that, the position of morality must be objective, absolute and universal. This objective moral view is well translated by the stream of realism, where moral facts (objective) and human self-understanding (subjective) are united.

The next question that becomes the final question, how do we get a formula for that moral objectivity? In short, we already know that moral truth is external and does not come from humans. The truth is outside of humans. So institutions like religion become central to internalizing that objective moral truth.

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